

A Note on the Benzoin-Benzil Change.

By K. MADHUSUDANAN PANDALAI.

It is well known that benzoin usually gives (i) benzoin anilide $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}\cdot(\text{NHPh})\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{Ph}$ when heated with aniline, (ii) benzoin-anilide anilide $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}\cdot(\text{NHPh})\cdot\text{C}\cdot(\text{NPh})\cdot\text{Ph}$ when heated with aniline hydrochloride at 160° , and (iii) diphenylindole when heated with aniline and zinc chloride (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 1336, 2640) or when heated with aniline and aniline hydrochloride with a fractionating column (Fennel and Plant, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2872; Japp and Murray, *ibid.*, 1894, 65, 889).

In an attempt to prepare some 2:3-diphenylindole by the method of Fennel and Plant (*loc. cit.*) it has been found that the product obtained is contaminated by small quantities of a crystalline substance identified to be benzil. The clue obtained here of obtaining this diketone from the reaction mixture has been worked out and it has been found that by modifying Fennel and Plants' method by dispensing with the use of a fractionating column, benzoin gives with aniline hydrochloride a mixture of benzil with small quantities of diphenyl.

The mechanism of oxidation of benzoin to benzil here seems to proceed according to the following scheme and the fact that all the products formed have been identified favours this explanation.

The presence of *isobenzoin* is proved by the fact that benzoin reduces acid chlorides according to the following equation (*cf.* Klinger, *Ber.*, 1890, 24, 1268; 1898, 31, 1217).

It should be admitted that aniline and aniline hydrochloride mixture has no oxidising action on secondary alcoholic groups, as the effects observed with benzoin could not be duplicated so as to get similar α -diketones from corresponding alcohols, cuminil from cuminoil, anisil from anisoil, furil from furoil and piperil from piperoin could not be obtained. It, therefore, seems compatible to attribute this apparent anomalous action of benzoin to (i) its highly tautomeric nature, (ii) its selective reactivity to reagents, and (iii) its peculiar susceptibility to variations in experimental conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Benzoin (16 g.), aniline (24 g.) and aniline hydrochloride (24 g.) were refluxed on a water-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ to 2 hours. Ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid was added to the yellow liquid, when a syrupy, yellowish mass separated. This was filtered, washed several times with dilute hydrochloric acid and dried. On extracting this with hot alcohol repeatedly (charcoal) a dark brown oil separated and fine needles crystallised from the supernatant liquid. The supernatant liquid was decanted and again treated with animal charcoal, when benzil was obtained as bright yellowish needles, m.p. 95° , yield 12 g. The *osazone* is obtained as yellow crystals, m.p. 215° ; the *semicarbazone*, m.p. 175° (benzil monosemicarbazone, m.p. 175°). That the two keto groups are adjacent in this product was proved by the fact that it was capable of condensing with *o*-phenylenediamine to give a quinoxaline derivative (Mosettig and Kamp, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 3332).

The mother liquor was now made alkaline by sodium hydroxide solution, the separated aniline removed and the solution steam distilled, when a white crystalline substance was obtained in the distillate. This was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 71° , yield 3 g. It was identified to be diphenyl (dibromo derivative, m.p. 164° , dinitro derivative, m.p. 233°).

On keeping the brown oil mentioned above for a week, a further quantity (1 g.) of diphenyl formed on the surface of it. The oily mass could not be identified. It is soluble in hot organic solvents, *e.g.*, ether, alcohol, benzene, etc. The steam distilled solution on qualitative examination revealed the presence of the chlorides of sodium and ammonium.